

S1 – Supplementary Material – Tables

Index of Tables

S1-Table 1: Summary statistics for self-reported friendship and advice seeking scores (interpolated) by organizational context.....	3
S1-Table 2: QAP correlation coefficients between advice-seeking and friendship networks. Significant correlations at $p < .05$ bolded and underlined.....	3
S1-Table 3: Quantiles of correlation coefficients at lower and upper bound for simulated reference distributions.....	3
S1-Table 4: Spearman's rho correlation coefficients for cumulative BT detections and friendship scores. Peak correlations bolded and underlined.....	4
S1-Table 5: Spearman's rho correlation coefficients for cumulative BT detections and advice-seeking score. Peak correlations bolded and underlined.....	5
S1-Table 6: Spearman's rho correlation coefficients for discrete BT detections and friendship scores. Peak correlations bolded and underlined.....	6
S1-Table 7: Spearman's rho correlation coefficients for discrete BT detections and advice-seeking scores. Peak correlations bolded and underlined.....	7
S1-Table 8: Differences between university-based teams and research lab-based teams for cumulative BT detections and friendship scores based upon cocor-test.....	8
S1-Table 9: Differences between university-based teams and private company-based teams for cumulative BT detections and friendship scores based upon cocor-test.....	9
S1-Table 10: Differences between research lab-based teams and private company-based teams for cumulative BT detections and friendship scores based upon cocor-test.....	10
S1-Table 11: Differences between university-based teams and research lab-based teams for cumulative BT detections and advice-seeking scores based upon cocor-test.....	11
S1-Table 12: Differences between university-based teams and private company-based teams for cumulative BT detections and advice-seeking scores based upon cocor-test.....	12
S1-Table 13: Differences between research lab-based teams and private company-based teams for cumulative BT detections and advice-seeking scores based upon cocor-test.....	13
S1-Table 14: Differences between university-based teams and research lab-based teams for discrete BT detections and friendship scores based upon cocor-test.....	14
S1-Table 15: Differences between university-based teams and private company-based teams for discrete BT detections and friendship scores based upon cocor-test.....	15

S1-Table 16: Differences between private company-based teams and research lab-based teams for discrete BT detections and friendship scores based upon cocor-test..... 16

S1-Table 17: Differences between university-based teams and research lab-based teams for discrete BT detections and advice-seeking scores based upon cocor-test..... 17

S1-Table 18: Differences between university-based teams and private company-based teams for discrete BT detections and advice-seeking scores based upon cocor-test..... 18

S1-Table 19: Differences between private company-based teams and research lab-based teams for discrete BT detections and advice-seeking scores based upon cocor-test..... 19

S1-Table 1: Summary statistics for self-reported friendship and advice seeking scores (interpolated) by organizational context.

Organization	Self-reported measure	Min.	1 st quant.	Median	3 rd quant.	Max.	Mean
All teams	Advice	2	4.0	6.0	8.00	10.0	5.93
All teams	Friendship	1	1.5	2.0	3.00	5.0	2.17
University	Advice	2	3.0	5.0	7.25	10.0	5.20
University	Friendship	1	1.0	1.5	2.00	3.5	1.55
Research labs	Advice	2	5.0	6.0	8.00	10.0	6.25
Research labs	Friendship	1	1.5	2.5	3.00	5.0	2.46
Private company	Advice	2	5.0	6.0	8.00	10.0	6.37
Private company	Friendship	1	2.0	2.5	3.00	4.0	2.48

S1-Table 2: QAP correlation coefficients between advice-seeking and friendship networks. Significant correlations at $p < .05$ bolded and underlined.

Team	cor.	$p(f(\text{perm}) \geq f(d))$	$p(f(\text{perm}) \leq f(d))$
1	0.399	<u>0.036</u>	0.968
2	0.215	0.182	0.823
3	0.331	0.054	0.957
4	0.391	<u>0.031</u>	0.975
5	0.226	0.141	0.859
6	-0.057	0.581	0.419
71	0.247	0.204	0.821
72	0.176	0.294	0.713
8	0.225	0.232	0.790

S1-Table 3: Quantiles of correlation coefficients at lower and upper bound for simulated reference distributions.

Organization	Self-reported measure	0.5%	2.5%	97.5%	99.5%
All teams	Advice	-0.189	-0.129	0.240	0.282
All teams	Friendship	-0.149	-0.08	0.424	0.464
University	Advice	-0.436	-0.323	0.313	0.401
University	Friendship	-0.461	-0.330	0.345	0.428
Research labs	Advice	-0.360	-0.304	0.120	0.187
Research labs	Friendship	-0.218	-0.143	0.272	0.334
Private company	Advice	-0.419	-0.303	0.356	0.457
Private company	Friendship	-0.425	-0.318	0.347	0.434

S1-Table 4: Spearman's rho correlation coefficients for cumulative BT detections and friendship scores. Peak correlations bolded and underlined.

RSSI Interval	All teams		University		Research Labs		Private Company	
	rho	# dyads						
-53 : -53	0.159	163	0.039	36	0.146	91	0.106	36
-53 : -54	0.240	198	0.157	43	0.241	110	0.152	45
-53 : -55	0.215	217	0.060	45	0.258	122	0.224	50
-53 : -56	0.236	225	0.124	47	0.267	124	0.307	54
-53 : -57	0.249	231	0.118	47	0.305	126	0.283	58
-53 : -58	0.277	239	0.141	51	0.322	130	0.291	58
-53 : -59	0.289	246	0.108	51	0.345	134	<u>0.334</u>	61
-53 : -60	0.310	250	0.181	53	0.356	134	0.313	63
-53 : -61	0.315	250	0.179	53	0.357	134	0.321	63
-53 : -62	0.321	253	0.145	55	0.358	135	0.314	63
-53 : -63	0.337	255	0.159	57	0.367	135	0.305	63
-53 : -64	0.344	255	0.157	57	0.368	135	0.313	63
-53 : -65	0.358	258	0.203	59	0.366	136	0.297	63
-53 : -66	0.371	260	0.178	61	0.372	136	0.286	63
-53 : -67	0.378	260	0.174	61	0.374	136	0.283	63
-53 : -68	0.400	262	0.205	63	0.385	136	0.284	63
-53 : -69	0.405	262	<u>0.208</u>	63	0.390	136	0.282	63
-53 : -70	0.410	262	<u>0.208</u>	63	0.395	136	0.287	63
-53 : -71	0.419	264	0.164	65	0.399	136	0.287	63
-53 : -72	0.419	264	0.164	65	0.397	136	0.276	63
-53 : -73	0.433	266	0.152	67	0.400	136	0.288	63
-53 : -74	0.440	267	0.174	68	0.402	136	0.285	63
-53 : -75	0.443	267	0.165	68	0.408	136	0.282	63
-53 : -76	0.450	269	0.152	70	0.413	136	0.285	63
-53 : -77	0.452	269	0.148	70	0.413	136	0.287	63
-53 : -78	0.457	269	0.135	70	0.421	136	0.290	63
-53 : -79	0.459	270	0.104	71	0.421	136	0.300	63
-53 : -80	0.467	271	0.090	72	0.422	136	0.312	63
-53 : -81	0.476	272	0.110	73	0.430	136	0.310	63
-53 : -82	0.479	272	0.096	73	0.434	136	0.303	63
-53 : -83	0.495	275	0.070	76	0.444	136	0.308	63
-53 : -84	0.498	275	0.070	76	0.450	136	0.314	63
-53 : -85	0.501	275	0.069	76	0.454	136	0.307	63
-53 : -86	0.503	275	0.066	76	0.457	136	0.315	63
-53 : -87	0.506	275	0.055	76	0.460	136	0.311	63
-53 : -88	0.511	275	0.054	76	0.467	136	0.297	63
-53 : -89	<u>0.516</u>	276	0.074	77	<u>0.469</u>	136	0.301	63
-53 : -90	<u>0.516</u>	276	0.073	77	<u>0.469</u>	136	0.295	63
-53 : -91	0.515	276	0.072	77	<u>0.469</u>	136	0.295	63

S1-Table 5: Spearman's rho correlation coefficients for cumulative BT detections and advice-seeking score. Peak correlations bolded and underlined.

RSSI Interval	All teams		University		Research Labs		Private Company	
	rho	# dyads						
-53 : -53	0.314	163	0.269	36	0.285	91	0.384	36
-53 : -54	0.339	198	0.442	43	0.289	110	0.391	45
-53 : -55	0.321	217	0.405	45	0.307	122	0.291	50
-53 : -56	0.359	225	0.455	47	0.330	124	0.342	54
-53 : -57	0.372	231	0.455	47	0.329	126	0.410	58
-53 : -58	0.386	239	0.438	51	<u>0.338</u>	130	0.400	58
-53 : -59	0.389	246	0.448	51	0.336	134	0.444	61
-53 : -60	0.393	250	0.436	53	0.332	134	<u>0.458</u>	63
-53 : -61	0.390	250	0.463	53	0.325	134	0.437	63
-53 : -62	0.404	253	0.536	55	0.324	135	0.417	63
-53 : -63	0.414	255	0.562	57	0.326	135	0.386	63
-53 : -64	0.409	255	0.566	57	0.320	135	0.388	63
-53 : -65	0.419	258	0.598	59	0.325	136	0.368	63
-53 : -66	<u>0.424</u>	260	0.603	61	0.322	136	0.369	63
-53 : -67	0.421	260	<u>0.613</u>	61	0.313	136	0.379	63
-53 : -68	0.405	262	0.564	63	0.306	136	0.372	63
-53 : -69	0.399	262	0.570	63	0.296	136	0.373	63
-53 : -70	0.393	262	0.570	63	0.288	136	0.367	63
-53 : -71	0.385	264	0.534	65	0.276	136	0.378	63
-53 : -72	0.382	264	0.532	65	0.274	136	0.384	63
-53 : -73	0.382	266	0.561	67	0.259	136	0.381	63
-53 : -74	0.387	267	0.578	68	0.256	136	0.384	63
-53 : -75	0.380	267	0.582	68	0.247	136	0.387	63
-53 : -76	0.384	269	0.585	70	0.241	136	0.393	63
-53 : -77	0.376	269	0.596	70	0.227	136	0.387	63
-53 : -78	0.365	269	0.605	70	0.212	136	0.390	63
-53 : -79	0.366	270	0.612	71	0.203	136	0.390	63
-53 : -80	0.354	271	0.584	72	0.187	136	0.383	63
-53 : -81	0.350	272	0.589	73	0.177	136	0.374	63
-53 : -82	0.344	272	0.582	73	0.171	136	0.359	63
-53 : -83	0.354	275	0.600	76	0.161	136	0.348	63
-53 : -84	0.351	275	0.597	76	0.155	136	0.341	63
-53 : -85	0.347	275	0.594	76	0.152	136	0.341	63
-53 : -86	0.342	275	0.594	76	0.150	136	0.324	63
-53 : -87	0.338	275	0.591	76	0.144	136	0.321	63
-53 : -88	0.332	275	0.583	76	0.139	136	0.310	63
-53 : -89	0.329	276	0.559	77	0.138	136	0.306	63
-53 : -90	0.328	276	0.556	77	0.138	136	0.307	63
-53 : -91	0.327	276	0.556	77	0.137	136	0.307	63

S1-Table 6: Spearman's rho correlation coefficients for discrete BT detections and friendship scores. Peak correlations bolded and underlined.

RSSI Level	All teams		University		Research Labs		Private Company	
	rho	# dyads						
-53	0.159	163	0.039	36	0.146	91	0.106	36
-54	0.168	185	0.053	36	0.185	105	0.117	44
-55	0.167	198	0.098	40	0.220	114	0.077	44
-56	0.253	199	-0.029	42	0.310	111	<u>0.339</u>	46
-57	0.275	205	0.112	39	0.358	110	0.309	56
-58	0.276	217	0.207	47	0.304	119	0.117	51
-59	0.218	218	0.095	43	0.265	120	0.201	55
-60	0.303	228	0.147	46	0.354	121	0.310	61
-61	0.298	229	0.207	46	0.335	124	0.297	59
-62	0.305	231	0.117	49	0.311	123	0.289	59
-63	0.347	240	0.189	51	0.392	130	0.219	59
-64	0.323	237	0.145	49	0.334	127	0.299	61
-65	0.362	247	0.206	53	0.353	132	0.245	62
-66	0.392	253	0.238	57	0.389	134	0.287	62
-67	0.370	250	0.179	53	0.383	135	0.250	62
-68	0.402	252	0.188	57	0.395	133	0.286	62
-69	0.400	254	0.161	56	0.404	135	0.259	63
-70	0.397	253	0.070	55	0.418	135	0.313	63
-71	0.402	252	0.206	54	0.374	135	0.298	63
-72	0.375	249	0.173	52	0.373	134	0.279	63
-73	0.447	260	0.123	61	0.426	136	0.282	63
-74	0.440	253	<u>0.279</u>	55	0.427	135	0.282	63
-75	0.442	255	0.097	57	0.429	135	0.294	63
-76	0.449	257	0.233	59	0.436	135	0.281	63
-77	0.424	255	0.058	56	0.406	136	0.288	63
-78	0.472	264	0.073	65	0.449	136	0.256	63
-79	0.460	257	0.163	59	0.420	135	0.186	63
-80	0.477	265	0.025	67	0.434	135	0.169	63
-81	0.486	264	0.156	65	0.447	136	0.164	63
-82	0.480	260	0.166	62	0.430	135	0.110	63
-83	0.490	268	0.020	70	0.451	135	0.060	63
-84	0.488	257	0.101	60	<u>0.478</u>	134	0.069	63
-85	0.495	266	0.197	68	0.452	135	-0.015	63
-86	0.485	264	0.042	66	0.469	135	-0.022	63
-87	<u>0.526</u>	265	0.234	66	0.472	136	-0.059	63
-88	0.482	266	0.099	68	0.466	135	-0.089	63
-89	0.474	258	0.176	62	0.453	133	-0.038	63
-90	0.463	255	0.175	58	0.439	134	-0.057	63
-91	0.385	227	0.188	42	0.379	124	-0.116	61

S1-Table 7: Spearman's rho correlation coefficients for discrete BT detections and advice-seeking scores. Peak correlations bolded and underlined.

RSSI Level	All teams		University		Research Labs		Private Company	
	rho	# dyads						
-53	0.314	163	0.269	36	0.285	91	0.384	36
-54	0.294	185	0.328	36	0.227	105	<u>0.421</u>	44
-55	0.297	198	0.281	40	<u>0.316</u>	114	0.280	44
-56	0.345	199	0.557	42	0.238	111	0.385	46
-57	0.343	205	0.497	39	0.287	110	0.357	56
-58	0.343	217	0.489	47	0.297	119	0.253	51
-59	0.338	218	0.470	43	0.310	120	0.288	55
-60	0.327	228	0.475	46	0.257	121	0.326	61
-61	0.289	229	0.448	46	0.224	124	0.289	59
-62	0.363	231	0.543	49	0.314	123	0.271	59
-63	<u>0.374</u>	240	<u>0.661</u>	51	0.283	130	0.260	59
-64	0.287	237	0.428	49	0.214	127	0.304	61
-65	0.354	247	0.538	53	0.306	132	0.285	62
-66	0.355	253	0.521	57	0.268	134	0.344	62
-67	0.330	250	0.553	53	0.257	135	0.315	62
-68	0.327	252	0.538	57	0.256	133	0.306	62
-69	0.300	254	0.437	56	0.225	135	0.334	63
-70	0.304	253	0.548	55	0.191	135	0.343	63
-71	0.250	252	0.350	54	0.174	135	0.394	63
-72	0.290	249	0.479	52	0.214	134	0.375	63
-73	0.287	260	0.544	61	0.157	136	0.364	63
-74	0.232	253	0.452	55	0.107	135	0.353	63
-75	0.221	255	0.388	57	0.135	135	0.281	63
-76	0.231	257	0.389	59	0.128	135	0.326	63
-77	0.203	255	0.394	56	0.109	136	0.296	63
-78	0.244	264	0.458	65	0.112	136	0.265	63
-79	0.171	257	0.336	59	0.071	135	0.179	63
-80	0.214	265	0.385	67	0.077	135	0.159	63
-81	0.202	264	0.399	65	0.073	136	0.140	63
-82	0.167	260	0.332	62	0.042	135	0.098	63
-83	0.207	268	0.397	70	0.048	135	0.031	63
-84	0.132	257	0.237	60	0.057	134	0.012	63
-85	0.160	266	0.303	68	0.032	135	-0.013	63
-86	0.133	264	0.256	66	0.021	135	-0.050	63
-87	0.149	265	0.216	66	0.039	136	-0.076	63
-88	0.130	266	0.184	68	0.035	135	-0.131	63
-89	0.052	258	0.021	62	0.024	133	-0.218	63
-90	0.095	255	0.129	58	0.024	134	-0.208	63
-91	0.033	227	0.040	42	-0.032	124	-0.145	61

S1-Table 8: Differences between university-based teams and research lab-based teams for cumulative BT detections and friendship scores based upon cocor-test.

RSSI interval	University	Research Labs	Difference	CI	p-value
-53 : -53	0.3150	0.1044	0.2105	[-0.1751, 0.55]	0.2784
-53 : -54	0.3250	0.1337	0.1913	[-0.1563, 0.5003]	0.2741
-53 : -55	0.3026	0.1451	0.1575	[-0.1807, 0.4607]	0.3542
-53 : -56	0.3069	0.1479	0.1591	[-0.172, 0.4566]	0.3394
-53 : -57	0.2769	0.1583	0.1186	[-0.2139, 0.4204]	0.4780
-53 : -58	0.2555	0.1657	0.0898	[-0.2316, 0.3858]	0.5787
-53 : -59	0.2392	0.1758	0.0634	[-0.2573, 0.3602]	0.6944
-53 : -60	0.2448	0.1861	0.0587	[-0.2563, 0.3509]	0.7112
-53 : -61	0.2357	0.1920	0.0437	[-0.2715, 0.3372]	0.7828
-53 : -62	0.2195	0.1987	0.0208	[-0.29, 0.3126]	0.8945
-53 : -63	0.2191	0.2085	0.0106	[-0.2953, 0.2989]	0.9453
-53 : -64	0.2150	0.2140	0.0010	[-0.3048, 0.2897]	0.9949
-53 : -65	0.2354	0.2228	0.0126	[-0.2875, 0.2949]	0.9334
-53 : -66	0.2436	0.2297	0.0140	[-0.2814, 0.292]	0.9252
-53 : -67	0.2514	0.2366	0.0148	[-0.2798, 0.2916]	0.9202
-53 : -68	0.2795	0.2450	0.0345	[-0.2542, 0.3044]	0.8119
-53 : -69	0.2900	0.2505	0.0395	[-0.2481, 0.3077]	0.7840
-53 : -70	0.2989	0.2612	0.0377	[-0.2486, 0.3043]	0.7925
-53 : -71	0.2995	0.2661	0.0334	[-0.249, 0.2973]	0.8133
-53 : -72	0.3071	0.2715	0.0356	[-0.2459, 0.2981]	0.8007
-53 : -73	0.3177	0.2837	0.0340	[-0.2426, 0.2922]	0.8059
-53 : -74	0.3270	0.2879	0.0391	[-0.2348, 0.2947]	0.7753
-53 : -75	0.3307	0.2968	0.0339	[-0.2391, 0.2885]	0.8039
-53 : -76	0.3309	0.3035	0.0274	[-0.2421, 0.2797]	0.8389
-53 : -77	0.3308	0.3085	0.0223	[-0.2469, 0.2743]	0.8683
-53 : -78	0.3326	0.3203	0.0123	[-0.256, 0.2634]	0.9270
-53 : -79	0.3251	0.3269	-0.0018	[-0.2688, 0.2491]	0.9892
-53 : -80	0.3236	0.3395	-0.0160	[-0.2808, 0.2334]	0.9039
-53 : -81	0.3269	0.3460	-0.0191	[-0.2817, 0.2285]	0.8842
-53 : -82	0.3241	0.3540	-0.0299	[-0.2922, 0.2176]	0.8193
-53 : -83	0.3147	0.3704	-0.0558	[-0.3136, 0.1891]	0.6644
-53 : -84	0.3127	0.3762	-0.0635	[-0.3212, 0.1812]	0.6204
-53 : -85	0.3093	0.3841	-0.0748	[-0.3321, 0.1699]	0.5592
-53 : -86	0.3056	0.3909	-0.0852	[-0.3423, 0.1594]	0.5050
-53 : -87	0.3035	0.3967	-0.0932	[-0.35, 0.1513]	0.4652
-53 : -88	0.2993	0.4053	-0.1060	[-0.3625, 0.1384]	0.4051
-53 : -89	0.3030	0.4074	-0.1044	[-0.3591, 0.1385]	0.4092
-53 : -90	0.3015	0.4091	-0.1077	[-0.3624, 0.1353]	0.3947
-53 : -91	0.3012	0.4094	-0.1083	[-0.363, 0.1347]	0.3921

S1-Table 9: Differences between university-based teams and private company-based teams for cumulative BT detections and friendship scores based upon cocor-test.

RSSI interval	University	Private company	Difference	CI	p-value
-53 : -53	0.3150	0.1251	0.1899	[-0.2634, 0.6207]	0.4159
-53 : -54	0.3250	0.1314	0.1936	[-0.2135, 0.5808]	0.3533
-53 : -55	0.3026	0.1525	0.1501	[-0.2419, 0.5251]	0.4547
-53 : -56	0.3069	0.1798	0.1271	[-0.2504, 0.4894]	0.5106
-53 : -57	0.2769	0.1711	0.1058	[-0.2692, 0.4652]	0.5814
-53 : -58	0.2555	0.1522	0.1033	[-0.2651, 0.4595]	0.5849
-53 : -59	0.2392	0.1623	0.0769	[-0.2876, 0.4301]	0.6811
-53 : -60	0.2448	0.1686	0.0761	[-0.2809, 0.4224]	0.6778
-53 : -61	0.2357	0.1669	0.0688	[-0.2888, 0.4162]	0.7080
-53 : -62	0.2195	0.1665	0.0529	[-0.3012, 0.3994]	0.7717
-53 : -63	0.2191	0.1628	0.0563	[-0.2944, 0.4001]	0.7555
-53 : -64	0.2150	0.1652	0.0497	[-0.3009, 0.394]	0.7832
-53 : -65	0.2354	0.1661	0.0693	[-0.2769, 0.4087]	0.6976
-53 : -66	0.2436	0.1733	0.0703	[-0.2714, 0.4063]	0.6896
-53 : -67	0.2514	0.1786	0.0728	[-0.268, 0.4078]	0.6782
-53 : -68	0.2795	0.1922	0.0872	[-0.2476, 0.4165]	0.6126
-53 : -69	0.2900	0.2012	0.0889	[-0.2444, 0.4166]	0.6041
-53 : -70	0.2989	0.2144	0.0844	[-0.2469, 0.4107]	0.6203
-53 : -71	0.2995	0.2249	0.0747	[-0.2525, 0.3985]	0.6578
-53 : -72	0.3071	0.2326	0.0745	[-0.2513, 0.3971]	0.6571
-53 : -73	0.3177	0.2488	0.0689	[-0.2514, 0.3877]	0.6764
-53 : -74	0.3270	0.2524	0.0746	[-0.2432, 0.3913]	0.6488
-53 : -75	0.3307	0.2622	0.0685	[-0.2479, 0.3841]	0.6748
-53 : -76	0.3309	0.2691	0.0618	[-0.2511, 0.3753]	0.7024
-53 : -77	0.3308	0.2759	0.0549	[-0.2572, 0.3681]	0.7336
-53 : -78	0.3326	0.2845	0.0481	[-0.2628, 0.3605]	0.7650
-53 : -79	0.3251	0.2873	0.0377	[-0.2721, 0.35]	0.8141
-53 : -80	0.3236	0.2894	0.0342	[-0.2743, 0.3457]	0.8306
-53 : -81	0.3269	0.2902	0.0367	[-0.2702, 0.347]	0.8176
-53 : -82	0.3241	0.2889	0.0352	[-0.2721, 0.3459]	0.8252
-53 : -83	0.3147	0.2848	0.0299	[-0.2751, 0.3397]	0.8504
-53 : -84	0.3127	0.2839	0.0288	[-0.2765, 0.3389]	0.8560
-53 : -85	0.3093	0.2788	0.0305	[-0.2757, 0.3413]	0.8481
-53 : -86	0.3056	0.2742	0.0314	[-0.2755, 0.3429]	0.8439
-53 : -87	0.3035	0.2695	0.0340	[-0.2737, 0.346]	0.8315
-53 : -88	0.2993	0.2612	0.0381	[-0.2709, 0.351]	0.8125
-53 : -89	0.3030	0.2598	0.0432	[-0.2646, 0.3551]	0.7870
-53 : -90	0.3015	0.2585	0.0429	[-0.2651, 0.355]	0.7886
-53 : -91	0.3012	0.2581	0.0431	[-0.265, 0.3552]	0.7878

S1-Table 10: Differences between research lab-based teams and private company-based teams for cumulative BT detections and friendship scores based upon cocor-test.

RSSI interval	Research lab	Private company	Difference	CI	p-value
-53 : -53	0.1044	0.1251	-0.0207	[-0.3946, 0.3711]	0.9182
-53 : -54	0.1337	0.1314	0.0023	[-0.3334, 0.3519]	0.9897
-53 : -55	0.1451	0.1525	-0.0074	[-0.3235, 0.3234]	0.9650
-53 : -56	0.1479	0.1798	-0.0320	[-0.336, 0.288]	0.8440
-53 : -57	0.1583	0.1711	-0.0128	[-0.3101, 0.2976]	0.9355
-53 : -58	0.1657	0.1522	0.0135	[-0.2843, 0.3225]	0.9318
-53 : -59	0.1758	0.1623	0.0135	[-0.2766, 0.3149]	0.9297
-53 : -60	0.1861	0.1686	0.0175	[-0.2688, 0.3146]	0.9080
-53 : -61	0.1920	0.1669	0.0251	[-0.2613, 0.322]	0.8681
-53 : -62	0.1987	0.1665	0.0322	[-0.2537, 0.3284]	0.8308
-53 : -63	0.2085	0.1628	0.0457	[-0.2403, 0.3416]	0.7611
-53 : -64	0.2140	0.1652	0.0488	[-0.2369, 0.3443]	0.7453
-53 : -65	0.2228	0.1661	0.0567	[-0.2283, 0.3515]	0.7049
-53 : -66	0.2297	0.1733	0.0564	[-0.2275, 0.3507]	0.7055
-53 : -67	0.2366	0.1786	0.0580	[-0.2251, 0.3518]	0.6966
-53 : -68	0.2450	0.1922	0.0528	[-0.2285, 0.3458]	0.7214
-53 : -69	0.2505	0.2012	0.0494	[-0.2307, 0.3418]	0.7380
-53 : -70	0.2612	0.2144	0.0467	[-0.2313, 0.3381]	0.7500
-53 : -71	0.2661	0.2249	0.0413	[-0.2353, 0.3319]	0.7777
-53 : -72	0.2715	0.2326	0.0389	[-0.2364, 0.3289]	0.7892
-53 : -73	0.2837	0.2488	0.0349	[-0.2377, 0.3233]	0.8089
-53 : -74	0.2879	0.2524	0.0355	[-0.2365, 0.3235]	0.8053
-53 : -75	0.2968	0.2622	0.0346	[-0.2357, 0.3214]	0.8092
-53 : -76	0.3035	0.2691	0.0344	[-0.2346, 0.3203]	0.8097
-53 : -77	0.3085	0.2759	0.0326	[-0.2352, 0.3178]	0.8186
-53 : -78	0.3203	0.2845	0.0358	[-0.2302, 0.3196]	0.7999
-53 : -79	0.3269	0.2873	0.0395	[-0.2257, 0.3227]	0.7789
-53 : -80	0.3395	0.2894	0.0502	[-0.2141, 0.3324]	0.7203
-53 : -81	0.3460	0.2902	0.0558	[-0.208, 0.3375]	0.6898
-53 : -82	0.3540	0.2889	0.0650	[-0.1984, 0.3464]	0.6407
-53 : -83	0.3704	0.2848	0.0857	[-0.1774, 0.3662]	0.5368
-53 : -84	0.3762	0.2839	0.0924	[-0.1705, 0.3726]	0.5046
-53 : -85	0.3841	0.2788	0.1053	[-0.1578, 0.3853]	0.4463
-53 : -86	0.3909	0.2742	0.1167	[-0.1467, 0.3966]	0.3981
-53 : -87	0.3967	0.2695	0.1273	[-0.1364, 0.4071]	0.3563
-53 : -88	0.4053	0.2612	0.1441	[-0.1201, 0.4239]	0.2958
-53 : -89	0.4074	0.2598	0.1476	[-0.1166, 0.4273]	0.2840
-53 : -90	0.4091	0.2585	0.1506	[-0.1137, 0.4303]	0.2743
-53 : -91	0.4094	0.2581	0.1513	[-0.113, 0.431]	0.2719

S1-Table 11: Differences between university-based teams and research lab-based teams for cumulative BT detections and advice-seeking scores based upon cocor-test.

RSSI interval	University	Research labs	Difference	CI	p-value
-53 : -53	0.2880	0.2027	0.0853	[-0.2977, 0.4291]	0.6564
-53 : -54	0.3428	0.1979	0.1449	[-0.1977, 0.4493]	0.3978
-53 : -55	0.3639	0.2022	0.1617	[-0.1675, 0.4519]	0.3257
-53 : -56	0.3964	0.2037	0.1927	[-0.1254, 0.4719]	0.2267
-53 : -57	0.4058	0.2100	0.1957	[-0.1201, 0.4719]	0.2160
-53 : -58	0.4179	0.2171	0.2008	[-0.101, 0.4666]	0.1851
-53 : -59	0.4324	0.2201	0.2123	[-0.0859, 0.4734]	0.1565
-53 : -60	0.4298	0.2242	0.2056	[-0.0881, 0.4645]	0.1636
-53 : -61	0.4361	0.2252	0.2109	[-0.0817, 0.4685]	0.1517
-53 : -62	0.4627	0.2283	0.2343	[-0.049, 0.4838]	0.1013
-53 : -63	0.4839	0.2312	0.2527	[-0.0226, 0.4958]	0.0700
-53 : -64	0.4849	0.2311	0.2539	[-0.0213, 0.4968]	0.0687
-53 : -65	0.4956	0.2366	0.2590	[-0.0099, 0.4973]	0.0577
-53 : -66	0.5016	0.2370	0.2645	[2e-04, 0.4999]	0.0490
-53 : -67	0.4984	0.2347	0.2638	[-0.0013, 0.4998]	0.0502
-53 : -68	0.4542	0.2356	0.2186	[-0.0507, 0.4608]	0.1081
-53 : -69	0.4453	0.2331	0.2122	[-0.0586, 0.456]	0.1207
-53 : -70	0.4341	0.2323	0.2018	[-0.0707, 0.4476]	0.1421
-53 : -71	0.4132	0.2303	0.1830	[-0.0893, 0.4305]	0.1824
-53 : -72	0.4049	0.2292	0.1757	[-0.0977, 0.4247]	0.2020
-53 : -73	0.3963	0.2228	0.1734	[-0.0983, 0.4221]	0.2056
-53 : -74	0.3984	0.2215	0.1769	[-0.0932, 0.4242]	0.1942
-53 : -75	0.3885	0.2185	0.1700	[-0.1015, 0.419]	0.2143
-53 : -76	0.3858	0.2155	0.1703	[-0.0987, 0.418]	0.2097
-53 : -77	0.3800	0.2099	0.1700	[-0.0999, 0.4188]	0.2121
-53 : -78	0.3701	0.2031	0.1670	[-0.1045, 0.4174]	0.2230
-53 : -79	0.3703	0.1980	0.1723	[-0.098, 0.4219]	0.2071
-53 : -80	0.3597	0.1923	0.1674	[-0.103, 0.4178]	0.2205
-53 : -81	0.3624	0.1866	0.1758	[-0.0932, 0.4251]	0.1963
-53 : -82	0.3596	0.1796	0.1800	[-0.0897, 0.4299]	0.1871
-53 : -83	0.3712	0.1689	0.2022	[-0.0629, 0.4482]	0.1324
-53 : -84	0.3700	0.1662	0.2038	[-0.0616, 0.45]	0.1298
-53 : -85	0.3684	0.1612	0.2072	[-0.0586, 0.4537]	0.1242
-53 : -86	0.3661	0.1564	0.2098	[-0.0565, 0.4567]	0.1203
-53 : -87	0.3635	0.1523	0.2111	[-0.0556, 0.4585]	0.1186
-53 : -88	0.3616	0.1484	0.2132	[-0.0539, 0.4609]	0.1156
-53 : -89	0.3565	0.1472	0.2093	[-0.0571, 0.4569]	0.1215
-53 : -90	0.3565	0.1463	0.2102	[-0.0563, 0.4578]	0.1200
-53 : -91	0.3564	0.1461	0.2103	[-0.0562, 0.4579]	0.1198

S1-Table 12: Differences between university-based teams and private company-based teams for cumulative BT detections and advice-seeking scores based upon cocor-test.

RSSI interval	University	Private company	Difference	CI	p-value
-53 : -53	0.2880	0.3181	-0.0301	[-0.457, 0.3994]	0.8929
-53 : -54	0.3428	0.3846	-0.0418	[-0.413, 0.3287]	0.8274
-53 : -55	0.3639	0.3420	0.0219	[-0.3409, 0.3779]	0.9061
-53 : -56	0.3964	0.3600	0.0364	[-0.3097, 0.3737]	0.8363
-53 : -57	0.4058	0.3759	0.0299	[-0.3086, 0.3562]	0.8615
-53 : -58	0.4179	0.3659	0.0520	[-0.2764, 0.3724]	0.7556
-53 : -59	0.4324	0.3727	0.0596	[-0.2628, 0.3716]	0.7151
-53 : -60	0.4298	0.3805	0.0493	[-0.2664, 0.3554]	0.7579
-53 : -61	0.4361	0.3737	0.0624	[-0.2532, 0.3682]	0.6964
-53 : -62	0.4627	0.3694	0.0933	[-0.2148, 0.3932]	0.5510
-53 : -63	0.4839	0.3567	0.1273	[-0.1754, 0.4233]	0.4085
-53 : -64	0.4849	0.3498	0.1351	[-0.1683, 0.4317]	0.3814
-53 : -65	0.4956	0.3449	0.1507	[-0.1483, 0.4445]	0.3226
-53 : -66	0.5016	0.3456	0.1560	[-0.1388, 0.4474]	0.2996
-53 : -67	0.4984	0.3473	0.1511	[-0.144, 0.4428]	0.3155
-53 : -68	0.4542	0.3458	0.1084	[-0.1908, 0.4053]	0.4789
-53 : -69	0.4453	0.3459	0.0994	[-0.2009, 0.3976]	0.5179
-53 : -70	0.4341	0.3488	0.0853	[-0.2162, 0.3848]	0.5808
-53 : -71	0.4132	0.3557	0.0576	[-0.2427, 0.3577]	0.7089
-53 : -72	0.4049	0.3626	0.0424	[-0.2579, 0.343]	0.7837
-53 : -73	0.3963	0.3751	0.0211	[-0.2756, 0.3199]	0.8902
-53 : -74	0.3984	0.3773	0.0211	[-0.2736, 0.3186]	0.8895
-53 : -75	0.3885	0.3777	0.0108	[-0.285, 0.3096]	0.9436
-53 : -76	0.3858	0.3830	0.0028	[-0.2899, 0.2998]	0.9854
-53 : -77	0.3800	0.3869	-0.0069	[-0.2997, 0.2903]	0.9636
-53 : -78	0.3701	0.3901	-0.0200	[-0.3133, 0.2781]	0.8954
-53 : -79	0.3703	0.3894	-0.0191	[-0.3112, 0.2783]	0.8996
-53 : -80	0.3597	0.3854	-0.0257	[-0.3181, 0.2727]	0.8656
-53 : -81	0.3624	0.3841	-0.0216	[-0.3127, 0.2759]	0.8863
-53 : -82	0.3596	0.3808	-0.0213	[-0.3131, 0.2769]	0.8885
-53 : -83	0.3712	0.3699	0.0013	[-0.2875, 0.2973]	0.9932
-53 : -84	0.3700	0.3657	0.0042	[-0.2853, 0.3008]	0.9776
-53 : -85	0.3684	0.3590	0.0094	[-0.2812, 0.3069]	0.9504
-53 : -86	0.3661	0.3524	0.0137	[-0.278, 0.3121]	0.9281
-53 : -87	0.3635	0.3450	0.0185	[-0.2745, 0.318]	0.9033
-53 : -88	0.3616	0.3321	0.0294	[-0.2656, 0.3303]	0.8478
-53 : -89	0.3565	0.3276	0.0288	[-0.2661, 0.3301]	0.8508
-53 : -90	0.3565	0.3233	0.0332	[-0.2624, 0.3347]	0.8291
-53 : -91	0.3564	0.3225	0.0339	[-0.2617, 0.3356]	0.8253

S1-Table 13: Differences between research lab-based teams and private company-based teams for cumulative BT detections and advice-seeking scores based upon cocor-test.

RSSI interval	Private company	Research labs	Difference	CI	p-value
-53 : -53	0.2027	0.3181	-0.1154	[-0.4529, 0.265]	0.5436
-53 : -54	0.1979	0.3846	-0.1867	[-0.4789, 0.1444]	0.2605
-53 : -55	0.2022	0.3420	-0.1398	[-0.4256, 0.1778]	0.3797
-53 : -56	0.2037	0.3600	-0.1563	[-0.4318, 0.1489]	0.3077
-53 : -57	0.2100	0.3759	-0.1659	[-0.4323, 0.128]	0.2617
-53 : -58	0.2171	0.3659	-0.1488	[-0.4149, 0.1446]	0.3124
-53 : -59	0.2201	0.3727	-0.1526	[-0.4122, 0.1328]	0.2873
-53 : -60	0.2242	0.3805	-0.1563	[-0.4123, 0.1244]	0.2683
-53 : -61	0.2252	0.3737	-0.1485	[-0.4056, 0.133]	0.2940
-53 : -62	0.2283	0.3694	-0.1411	[-0.3983, 0.1404]	0.3185
-53 : -63	0.2312	0.3567	-0.1255	[-0.3847, 0.1573]	0.3767
-53 : -64	0.2311	0.3498	-0.1187	[-0.379, 0.1648]	0.4041
-53 : -65	0.2366	0.3449	-0.1083	[-0.3688, 0.1751]	0.4461
-53 : -66	0.2370	0.3456	-0.1085	[-0.3689, 0.1748]	0.4450
-53 : -67	0.2347	0.3473	-0.1126	[-0.3728, 0.1706]	0.4280
-53 : -68	0.2356	0.3458	-0.1102	[-0.3706, 0.1732]	0.4382
-53 : -69	0.2331	0.3459	-0.1127	[-0.3732, 0.1708]	0.4281
-53 : -70	0.2323	0.3488	-0.1165	[-0.3765, 0.1667]	0.4124
-53 : -71	0.2303	0.3557	-0.1254	[-0.3843, 0.1573]	0.3769
-53 : -72	0.2292	0.3626	-0.1334	[-0.3913, 0.1486]	0.3462
-53 : -73	0.2228	0.3751	-0.1523	[-0.4084, 0.1285]	0.2807
-53 : -74	0.2215	0.3773	-0.1557	[-0.4115, 0.1249]	0.2699
-53 : -75	0.2185	0.3777	-0.1592	[-0.415, 0.1216]	0.2597
-53 : -76	0.2155	0.3830	-0.1675	[-0.4225, 0.1127]	0.2350
-53 : -77	0.2099	0.3869	-0.1770	[-0.4315, 0.1031]	0.2098
-53 : -78	0.2031	0.3901	-0.1870	[-0.4412, 0.0931]	0.1855
-53 : -79	0.1980	0.3894	-0.1914	[-0.4458, 0.089]	0.1760
-53 : -80	0.1923	0.3854	-0.1931	[-0.4483, 0.0881]	0.1735
-53 : -81	0.1866	0.3841	-0.1974	[-0.453, 0.0842]	0.1650
-53 : -82	0.1796	0.3808	-0.2012	[-0.4575, 0.0811]	0.1582
-53 : -83	0.1689	0.3699	-0.2010	[-0.4592, 0.0832]	0.1615
-53 : -84	0.1662	0.3657	-0.1996	[-0.4586, 0.0851]	0.1653
-53 : -85	0.1612	0.3590	-0.1978	[-0.4579, 0.0879]	0.1707
-53 : -86	0.1564	0.3524	-0.1961	[-0.4574, 0.0905]	0.1757
-53 : -87	0.1523	0.3450	-0.1926	[-0.4551, 0.0949]	0.1849
-53 : -88	0.1484	0.3321	-0.1838	[-0.4483, 0.1052]	0.2082
-53 : -89	0.1472	0.3276	-0.1804	[-0.4457, 0.109]	0.2173
-53 : -90	0.1463	0.3233	-0.1770	[-0.443, 0.1128]	0.2267
-53 : -91	0.1461	0.3225	-0.1764	[-0.4424, 0.1136]	0.2285

S1-Table 14: Differences between university-based teams and research lab-based teams for discrete BT detections and friendship scores based upon cocor-test.

RSSI level	University	Research labs	Difference	CI	p-value
-53	0.3150	0.1044	0.2105	[-0.1751, 0.55]	0.2784
-54	0.3291	0.1325	0.1966	[-0.1797, 0.5241]	0.2977
-55	0.3366	0.1573	0.1793	[-0.1751, 0.4901]	0.3128
-56	0.2357	0.1525	0.0832	[-0.2731, 0.4101]	0.6433
-57	0.2113	0.1715	0.0397	[-0.3281, 0.379]	0.8305
-58	0.2855	0.1746	0.1109	[-0.2226, 0.414]	0.5079
-59	0.1964	0.1717	0.0247	[-0.3255, 0.3512]	0.8888
-60	0.1419	0.2206	-0.0786	[-0.4173, 0.2468]	0.6479
-61	0.1919	0.2128	-0.0209	[-0.3585, 0.2965]	0.9025
-62	0.1450	0.2091	-0.0641	[-0.3943, 0.2535]	0.7025
-63	0.1449	0.2629	-0.1180	[-0.4382, 0.191]	0.4667
-64	0.1704	0.2332	-0.0628	[-0.3904, 0.2492]	0.7044
-65	0.2721	0.2712	0.0009	[-0.3088, 0.2871]	0.9956
-66	0.2793	0.2604	0.0189	[-0.2812, 0.2973]	0.8995
-67	0.2758	0.2912	-0.0154	[-0.3228, 0.2683]	0.9198
-68	0.3363	0.2908	0.0455	[-0.2481, 0.3139]	0.7552
-69	0.3134	0.2866	0.0267	[-0.271, 0.2997]	0.8567
-70	0.2988	0.3537	-0.0549	[-0.3521, 0.2186]	0.7073
-71	0.3819	0.3004	0.0815	[-0.2122, 0.3447]	0.5753
-72	0.3455	0.3134	0.0321	[-0.2703, 0.3047]	0.8296
-73	0.3437	0.3308	0.0129	[-0.2687, 0.2717]	0.9264
-74	0.4098	0.3754	0.0344	[-0.2484, 0.2867]	0.8036
-75	0.3665	0.3706	-0.0041	[-0.2887, 0.2539]	0.9765
-76	0.3571	0.3585	-0.0013	[-0.2837, 0.2565]	0.9924
-77	0.3224	0.3141	0.0083	[-0.2866, 0.2782]	0.9544
-78	0.3121	0.3707	-0.0586	[-0.3333, 0.198]	0.6661
-79	0.3485	0.3516	-0.0030	[-0.2868, 0.2567]	0.9828
-80	0.2747	0.3771	-0.1024	[-0.3765, 0.1571]	0.4511
-81	0.2973	0.3782	-0.0809	[-0.3563, 0.1774]	0.5522
-82	0.2832	0.3786	-0.0955	[-0.3776, 0.169]	0.4931
-83	0.1908	0.4017	-0.2109	[-0.4825, 0.0538]	0.1212
-84	0.1963	0.4440	-0.2477	[-0.5341, 0.0276]	0.0794
-85	0.1890	0.4154	-0.2264	[-0.5004, 0.04]	0.0978
-86	0.1219	0.4367	-0.3149	[-0.5916, -0.0402]	0.0240
-87	0.2700	0.4316	-0.1616	[-0.4335, 0.0956]	0.2264
-88	0.0914	0.4308	-0.3393	[-0.613, -0.0644]	0.0148
-89	0.0942	0.4236	-0.3294	[-0.6144, -0.0445]	0.0227
-90	0.0818	0.3975	-0.3157	[-0.61, -0.0215]	0.0350
-91	0.2108	0.3139	-0.1030	[-0.4479, 0.2176]	0.5475

S1-Table 15: Differences between university-based teams and private company-based teams for discrete BT detections and friendship scores based upon cocor-test.

RSSI level	University	Private company	Difference	CI	p-value
-53	0.3150	0.1251	0.1899	[-0.2634, 0.6207]	0.4159
-54	0.3291	0.1016	0.2275	[-0.2075, 0.6296]	0.3051
-55	0.3366	0.0914	0.2452	[-0.176, 0.6377]	0.2541
-56	0.2357	0.1700	0.0657	[-0.3439, 0.4653]	0.7565
-57	0.2113	0.1649	0.0463	[-0.3591, 0.4353]	0.8240
-58	0.2855	0.0102	0.2752	[-0.1223, 0.6437]	0.1746
-59	0.1964	0.0749	0.1215	[-0.2798, 0.5047]	0.5555
-60	0.1419	0.1825	-0.0405	[-0.4176, 0.3333]	0.8361
-61	0.1919	0.1302	0.0618	[-0.3217, 0.4332]	0.7545
-62	0.1450	0.1484	-0.0034	[-0.3783, 0.3677]	0.9861
-63	0.1449	0.1192	0.0257	[-0.3471, 0.3933]	0.8941
-64	0.1704	0.1691	0.0013	[-0.3693, 0.3662]	0.9947
-65	0.2721	0.1575	0.1146	[-0.2431, 0.459]	0.5315
-66	0.2793	0.2245	0.0548	[-0.2881, 0.3914]	0.7559
-67	0.2758	0.2038	0.0720	[-0.2811, 0.415]	0.6908
-68	0.3363	0.2633	0.0730	[-0.2613, 0.4002]	0.6700
-69	0.3134	0.2443	0.0691	[-0.27, 0.4]	0.6909
-70	0.2988	0.3019	-0.0031	[-0.3389, 0.3276]	0.9856
-71	0.3819	0.3143	0.0676	[-0.2608, 0.3864]	0.6863
-72	0.3455	0.2929	0.0526	[-0.2865, 0.381]	0.7610
-73	0.3437	0.2978	0.0459	[-0.2755, 0.3641]	0.7809
-74	0.4098	0.3088	0.1010	[-0.2226, 0.4149]	0.5398
-75	0.3665	0.3318	0.0346	[-0.2874, 0.351]	0.8335
-76	0.3571	0.3018	0.0553	[-0.2677, 0.3734]	0.7383
-77	0.3224	0.2807	0.0417	[-0.2926, 0.3693]	0.8075
-78	0.3121	0.2601	0.0520	[-0.2703, 0.3726]	0.7544
-79	0.3485	0.2059	0.1427	[-0.192, 0.467]	0.4044
-80	0.2747	0.1566	0.1180	[-0.2146, 0.4446]	0.4903
-81	0.2973	0.1449	0.1523	[-0.1828, 0.4784]	0.3753
-82	0.2832	0.0928	0.1904	[-0.1543, 0.5209]	0.2800
-83	0.1908	0.0527	0.1380	[-0.2021, 0.4692]	0.4297
-84	0.1963	0.0587	0.1376	[-0.2163, 0.4795]	0.4486
-85	0.1890	-0.0230	0.2120	[-0.1344, 0.5422]	0.2313
-86	0.1219	-0.0348	0.1567	[-0.1936, 0.4941]	0.3833
-87	0.2700	-0.0655	0.3355	[-0.0116, 0.6569]	0.0576
-88	0.0914	-0.1006	0.1920	[-0.1568, 0.5249]	0.2820
-89	0.0942	-0.0605	0.1547	[-0.2018, 0.4977]	0.3976
-90	0.0818	-0.0682	0.1500	[-0.2128, 0.4992]	0.4209
-91	0.2108	-0.0990	0.3098	[-0.0923, 0.6754]	0.1302

S1-Table 16: Differences between private company-based teams and research lab-based teams for discrete BT detections and friendship scores based upon cocor-test.

RSSI level	Research labs	Private company	Difference	CI	p-value
-53	0.1044	0.1251	-0.0207	[-0.3946, 0.3711]	0.9182
-54	0.1325	0.1016	0.0309	[-0.3136, 0.3852]	0.8655
-55	0.1573	0.0914	0.0659	[-0.2751, 0.4152]	0.7140
-56	0.1525	0.1700	-0.0175	[-0.345, 0.3279]	0.9207
-57	0.1715	0.1649	0.0066	[-0.3022, 0.3267]	0.9678
-58	0.1746	0.0102	0.1643	[-0.1642, 0.4884]	0.3330
-59	0.1717	0.0749	0.0968	[-0.218, 0.4145]	0.5550
-60	0.2206	0.1825	0.0381	[-0.2542, 0.3411]	0.8044
-61	0.2128	0.1302	0.0826	[-0.2173, 0.3894]	0.5982
-62	0.2091	0.1484	0.0607	[-0.2378, 0.368]	0.6981
-63	0.2629	0.1192	0.1438	[-0.1532, 0.4459]	0.3513
-64	0.2332	0.1691	0.0641	[-0.2267, 0.3646]	0.6746
-65	0.2712	0.1575	0.1137	[-0.1735, 0.409]	0.4476
-66	0.2604	0.2245	0.0359	[-0.2431, 0.3292]	0.8079
-67	0.2912	0.2038	0.0874	[-0.1925, 0.3795]	0.5519
-68	0.2908	0.2633	0.0275	[-0.2453, 0.3173]	0.8495
-69	0.2866	0.2443	0.0424	[-0.2312, 0.3311]	0.7696
-70	0.3537	0.3019	0.0518	[-0.2101, 0.3323]	0.7092
-71	0.3004	0.3143	-0.0140	[-0.2769, 0.2689]	0.9210
-72	0.3134	0.2929	0.0204	[-0.2454, 0.3046]	0.8851
-73	0.3308	0.2978	0.0331	[-0.2304, 0.3152]	0.8134
-74	0.3754	0.3088	0.0666	[-0.193, 0.345]	0.6280
-75	0.3706	0.3318	0.0387	[-0.2175, 0.3154]	0.7765
-76	0.3585	0.3018	0.0567	[-0.205, 0.3369]	0.6828
-77	0.3141	0.2807	0.0334	[-0.2334, 0.3179]	0.8138
-78	0.3707	0.2601	0.1106	[-0.156, 0.3928]	0.4289
-79	0.3516	0.2059	0.1457	[-0.1295, 0.4321]	0.3091
-80	0.3771	0.1566	0.2205	[-0.059, 0.5065]	0.1252
-81	0.3782	0.1449	0.2333	[-0.047, 0.5191]	0.1052
-82	0.3786	0.0928	0.2858	[2e-04, 0.5717]	0.0498
-83	0.4017	0.0527	0.3489	[0.0615, 0.6323]	0.0166
-84	0.4440	0.0587	0.3853	[0.1009, 0.6661]	0.0073
-85	0.4154	-0.0230	0.4384	[0.1475, 0.7172]	0.0028
-86	0.4367	-0.0348	0.4715	[0.1815, 0.7479]	0.0012
-87	0.4316	-0.0655	0.4971	[0.2061, 0.7714]	0.0007
-88	0.4308	-0.1006	0.5313	[0.2393, 0.8028]	0.0003
-89	0.4236	-0.0605	0.4841	[0.1918, 0.76]	0.0010
-90	0.3975	-0.0682	0.4657	[0.1718, 0.7427]	0.0017
-91	0.3139	-0.0990	0.4128	[0.1067, 0.699]	0.0079

S1-Table 17: Differences between university-based teams and research lab-based teams for discrete BT detections and advice-seeking scores based upon cocor-test.

RSSI level	University	Research labs	Difference	CI	p-value
-53	0.2880	0.2027	0.0853	[-0.2977, 0.4291]	0.6564
-54	0.3387	0.1877	0.1511	[-0.2217, 0.4755]	0.4165
-55	0.3359	0.2157	0.1202	[-0.2315, 0.43]	0.4922
-56	0.4468	0.1783	0.2685	[-0.0628, 0.5526]	0.1078
-57	0.4455	0.2154	0.2301	[-0.1106, 0.5195]	0.1768
-58	0.4435	0.2157	0.2278	[-0.0839, 0.4994]	0.1459
-59	0.4793	0.2329	0.2464	[-0.0691, 0.5151]	0.1200
-60	0.4463	0.2180	0.2283	[-0.085, 0.4997]	0.1468
-61	0.4258	0.1995	0.2263	[-0.0903, 0.5012]	0.1548
-62	0.5055	0.2346	0.2709	[-0.0213, 0.524]	0.0671
-63	0.5581	0.2285	0.3296	[0.0559, 0.5661]	0.0190
-64	0.4093	0.2009	0.2084	[-0.1016, 0.4806]	0.1807
-65	0.4555	0.2447	0.2107	[-0.0782, 0.4647]	0.1467
-66	0.4462	0.2111	0.2350	[-0.0482, 0.4864]	0.1006
-67	0.3765	0.1999	0.1766	[-0.1256, 0.4459]	0.2443
-68	0.3027	0.2079	0.0947	[-0.2065, 0.3716]	0.5309
-69	0.2630	0.1803	0.0827	[-0.2244, 0.367]	0.5926
-70	0.2630	0.1850	0.0781	[-0.231, 0.3638]	0.6155
-71	0.1720	0.1641	0.0079	[-0.3079, 0.3084]	0.9605
-72	0.2104	0.1752	0.0352	[-0.2843, 0.3344]	0.8271
-73	0.2228	0.1477	0.0752	[-0.225, 0.3578]	0.6206
-74	0.1630	0.1244	0.0386	[-0.2767, 0.3389]	0.8096
-75	0.1631	0.1226	0.0405	[-0.2706, 0.3373]	0.7980
-76	0.1763	0.1191	0.0572	[-0.2497, 0.3491]	0.7140
-77	0.1735	0.0847	0.0889	[-0.225, 0.3859]	0.5777
-78	0.2048	0.0926	0.1122	[-0.1836, 0.392]	0.4551
-79	0.1492	0.0607	0.0885	[-0.2206, 0.3836]	0.5745
-80	0.2100	0.0832	0.1268	[-0.1662, 0.4038]	0.3942
-81	0.2020	0.0543	0.1477	[-0.1493, 0.4277]	0.3279
-82	0.2036	0.0294	0.1741	[-0.1289, 0.4582]	0.2584
-83	0.2389	0.0364	0.2025	[-0.086, 0.4724]	0.1672
-84	0.1479	0.0601	0.0878	[-0.2198, 0.3818]	0.5758
-85	0.2010	0.0220	0.1790	[-0.1144, 0.4554]	0.2303
-86	0.1397	0.0019	0.1378	[-0.1603, 0.4229]	0.3650
-87	0.1441	0.0235	0.1206	[-0.1767, 0.4052]	0.4264
-88	0.1590	0.0364	0.1225	[-0.1715, 0.4035]	0.4137
-89	0.0632	0.0216	0.0416	[-0.2628, 0.3402]	0.7907
-90	0.2254	0.0264	0.1990	[-0.1112, 0.4865]	0.2066
-91	0.1936	0.0000	0.1936	[-0.1637, 0.5214]	0.2869

S1-Table 18: Differences between university-based teams and private company-based teams for discrete BT detections and advice-seeking scores based upon cocor-test.

RSSI level	University	Private company	Difference	CI	p-value
-53	0.2880	0.3181	-0.0301	[-0.457, 0.3994]	0.8929
-54	0.3387	0.4131	-0.0744	[-0.4684, 0.3093]	0.7107
-55	0.3359	0.3316	0.0043	[-0.387, 0.3897]	0.9829
-56	0.4468	0.3622	0.0846	[-0.2778, 0.4386]	0.6470
-57	0.4455	0.3394	0.1060	[-0.2575, 0.4443]	0.5609
-58	0.4435	0.2920	0.1515	[-0.2011, 0.4936]	0.3996
-59	0.4793	0.3138	0.1655	[-0.1835, 0.4956]	0.3481
-60	0.4463	0.3127	0.1336	[-0.2065, 0.4548]	0.4366
-61	0.4258	0.2913	0.1345	[-0.2135, 0.4645]	0.4453
-62	0.5055	0.2809	0.2245	[-0.1041, 0.5379]	0.1782
-63	0.5581	0.2526	0.3056	[-0.0122, 0.6101]	0.0586
-64	0.4093	0.2787	0.1305	[-0.2116, 0.4568]	0.4522
-65	0.4555	0.2825	0.1730	[-0.1523, 0.4853]	0.2953
-66	0.4462	0.3218	0.1244	[-0.1898, 0.4314]	0.4373
-67	0.3765	0.3254	0.0511	[-0.2796, 0.3727]	0.7617
-68	0.3027	0.2955	0.0072	[-0.3262, 0.3369]	0.9667
-69	0.2630	0.3167	-0.0537	[-0.3881, 0.2793]	0.7557
-70	0.2630	0.3355	-0.0725	[-0.4067, 0.2604]	0.6742
-71	0.1720	0.3829	-0.2109	[-0.5448, 0.1301]	0.2278
-72	0.2104	0.3944	-0.1840	[-0.52, 0.1546]	0.2908
-73	0.2228	0.3784	-0.1556	[-0.4749, 0.1703]	0.3513
-74	0.1630	0.3629	-0.1998	[-0.5342, 0.1425]	0.2550
-75	0.1631	0.2912	-0.1281	[-0.467, 0.2168]	0.4709
-76	0.1763	0.3608	-0.1845	[-0.5111, 0.1507]	0.2826
-77	0.1735	0.3149	-0.1413	[-0.4793, 0.2023]	0.4243
-78	0.2048	0.2693	-0.0645	[-0.3915, 0.2674]	0.7057
-79	0.1492	0.2009	-0.0516	[-0.3967, 0.2959]	0.7743
-80	0.2100	0.1360	0.0740	[-0.2633, 0.4074]	0.6709
-81	0.2020	0.1488	0.0532	[-0.2861, 0.3893]	0.7618
-82	0.2036	0.0981	0.1054	[-0.2425, 0.4448]	0.5559
-83	0.2389	0.0209	0.2180	[-0.1223, 0.5436]	0.2102
-84	0.1479	-0.0160	0.1639	[-0.1945, 0.5077]	0.3724
-85	0.2010	-0.0343	0.2353	[-0.1112, 0.5637]	0.1836
-86	0.1397	-0.0582	0.1979	[-0.153, 0.5324]	0.2703
-87	0.1441	-0.1195	0.2636	[-0.088, 0.5933]	0.1415
-88	0.1590	-0.1653	0.3242	[-0.0244, 0.6463]	0.0677
-89	0.0632	-0.2454	0.3086	[-0.0454, 0.6375]	0.0870
-90	0.2254	-0.2746	0.5000	[0.142, 0.8158]	0.0062
-91	0.1936	-0.1920	0.3856	[-0.0164, 0.746]	0.0593

S1-Table 19: Differences between private company-based teams and research lab-based teams for discrete BT detections and advice-seeking scores based upon cocor-test.

RSSI level	Research labs	Private company	Difference	CI	p-value
-53	0.2027	0.3181	-0.1154	[-0.4529, 0.265]	0.5436
-54	0.1877	0.4131	-0.2255	[-0.5168, 0.1071]	0.1773
-55	0.2157	0.3316	-0.1159	[-0.4179, 0.2222]	0.4922
-56	0.1783	0.3622	-0.1839	[-0.4787, 0.1477]	0.2693
-57	0.2154	0.3394	-0.1240	[-0.4073, 0.1837]	0.4228
-58	0.2157	0.2920	-0.0764	[-0.3702, 0.2437]	0.6341
-59	0.2329	0.3138	-0.0809	[-0.3638, 0.2266]	0.5998
-60	0.2180	0.3127	-0.0947	[-0.3697, 0.2013]	0.5250
-61	0.1995	0.2913	-0.0919	[-0.3718, 0.2096]	0.5450
-62	0.2346	0.2809	-0.0463	[-0.3272, 0.2543]	0.7590
-63	0.2285	0.2526	-0.0241	[-0.3061, 0.2765]	0.8735
-64	0.2009	0.2787	-0.0778	[-0.3555, 0.2196]	0.6034
-65	0.2447	0.2825	-0.0378	[-0.3102, 0.2537]	0.7962
-66	0.2111	0.3218	-0.1106	[-0.3775, 0.1788]	0.4468
-67	0.1999	0.3254	-0.1255	[-0.3917, 0.1638]	0.3885
-68	0.2079	0.2955	-0.0876	[-0.3588, 0.2045]	0.5511
-69	0.1803	0.3167	-0.1364	[-0.4031, 0.1529]	0.3495
-70	0.1850	0.3355	-0.1505	[-0.4143, 0.1368]	0.2985
-71	0.1641	0.3829	-0.2188	[-0.4755, 0.0643]	0.1266
-72	0.1752	0.3944	-0.2192	[-0.4742, 0.0623]	0.1237
-73	0.1477	0.3784	-0.2308	[-0.4881, 0.0533]	0.1086
-74	0.1244	0.3629	-0.2385	[-0.4989, 0.0486]	0.1013
-75	0.1226	0.2912	-0.1685	[-0.4399, 0.1252]	0.2567
-76	0.1191	0.3608	-0.2417	[-0.5025, 0.0459]	0.0974
-77	0.0847	0.3149	-0.2302	[-0.4978, 0.0627]	0.1211
-78	0.0926	0.2693	-0.1767	[-0.4508, 0.1193]	0.2387
-79	0.0607	0.2009	-0.1401	[-0.4234, 0.1605]	0.3590
-80	0.0832	0.1360	-0.0528	[-0.3431, 0.2484]	0.7315
-81	0.0543	0.1488	-0.0945	[-0.3831, 0.2071]	0.5390
-82	0.0294	0.0981	-0.0687	[-0.3623, 0.2337]	0.6576
-83	0.0364	0.0209	0.0155	[-0.2837, 0.3157]	0.9207
-84	0.0601	-0.0160	0.0761	[-0.2255, 0.3742]	0.6250
-85	0.0220	-0.0343	0.0563	[-0.2454, 0.3538]	0.7177
-86	0.0019	-0.0582	0.0600	[-0.2422, 0.3563]	0.6994
-87	0.0235	-0.1195	0.1430	[-0.1601, 0.4334]	0.3560
-88	0.0364	-0.1653	0.2017	[-0.1016, 0.4876]	0.1918
-89	0.0216	-0.2454	0.2670	[-0.034, 0.5444]	0.0812
-90	0.0264	-0.2746	0.3011	[0.0021, 0.574]	0.0480
-91	0.0000	-0.1920	0.1920	[-0.1179, 0.4829]	0.2235